

How Spatial Temperature Datasets Help Us Understand Heat Vulnerability: Observations vs Urban Climate Modelling

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Summary

Choosing the appropriate environmental datasets for spatial vulnerability analyses is essential to ensure that risk is well-characterised and urban planning and mitigation measures are targeted effectively. For this purpose, we focus on the Greater London Area and compare daily mean, maximum, and minimum temperatures from three datasets.

Results show substantial differences in spatial temperature patterns, particularly at night, with modelled outputs capturing urban heat island effects more consistently across the city. When combined with socio-economic indicators, these discrepancies yield divergent vulnerability maps, underscoring the critical role of dataset selection in urban heat risk assessments and adaptation planning.

KEYWORDS:-Climate change, Heat risk, Deprivation, Spatial Vulnerability, Building stock

1. Introduction

Rising temperatures and more frequent extreme heat events pose an increasing threat to human health, particularly in temperate regions such as the UK, where infrastructure and buildings are primarily designed for colder conditions. As heat exposure is unevenly distributed within cities due to urban form and socio-economic factors, identifying which neighborhoods and populations are most affected is essential for effective and equitable adaptation planning (Cole et al., 2024).

Air temperature measurements from official meteorological networks, such as those operated by the UK Met Office, are often too sparse or located outside urban cores to capture fine-scale thermal variability and urban microclimate effects (Brousse et al., 2025; Wen et al., 2025).

In response, weather devices operated by individuals who share the data collected through crowdsourcing have emerged as a viable alternative for capturing high-resolution urban climate data and for model validation (Brousse et al., 2024; Mitchell and Fry, 2024). Nevertheless, whatever approach is used to retrieve temperature data, either the traditional meteorological station networks, the new personal weather station networks, or climate models, it is critical to assess the uncertainties associated with each method to

ensure the reliability of inputs required for spatial vulnerability assessments of the built environment (Njoku et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2014).

Such discrepancies hold significant implications for spatial vulnerability assessments of urban environments, since the selection of the temperature dataset profoundly affects the delineation of heat-exposed areas and vulnerable populations.

Against this background, this study quantifies how different temperature datasets shape urban heat vulnerability mapping across the Greater London Area (GLA). Temperatures from the Met Office HadUK-Grid and Crowd-Grid datasets, and high-resolution climate model simulations are compared for the 10th-25th July 2022. This period represents the second and most extreme heat wave the UK experienced during summer 2022 (Agency, 2025), with temperatures exceeding 40 °C on July 19th for the first time in the UK (Kendon et al., 2023; Simpson et al., 2024), offering a unique case study to examine the sensitivity of different data sources and their implications for spatial vulnerability assessment and the evaluation of targeted adaptation strategies.

2. Data and Methods

Specifically, the analysis compares daily mean, maximum, and minimum temperatures for the 10th-25th July 2022 from the various temperature datasets to assess their suitability for the following spatial vulnerability analysis of the Greater London Area. The characteristics of each dataset are described in the following table.

High-resolution WRF simulations incorporating an urban canopy parameterization scheme were used; a detailed description of the model configuration and evaluation is provided in (Simpson et al., 2024). Notably, the model's performance was evaluated against the official HadUK-Grid dataset and Met Office station observations across the UK, demonstrating its ability to reproduce observed spatial thermal patterns during extreme heat events.

Table 1 Dataset characteristics

Dataset	Type	Variable	Spatial Resolution	Time Resolution	Projections	Data Source
WRF model	Model	tas, tasmx, tasmin	1km x 1km	Hourly	Lat / Lon	Boundary conditions from ERA-5 Reanalysis dataset
Crowd-Grid	Observation	tas, tasmx, tasmin	1km x 1km	Daily	British National Grid EPSG:27700 - OSGB36	Met Office land observation network, crowdsourced weather observations (WOW), roadside networks from UK highway agencies
HadUK-Grid	Observation	tas, tasmx, tasmin	1km x 1km	Daily	British National Grid EPSG:27700 - OSGB36	Met Office land observation network

Given the hourly temporal resolution of the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model outputs, the first step of the comparison was to aggregate the hourly simulated values to extract daily mean, maximum, and minimum temperatures, thereby creating a temporal resolution consistent with the observational datasets for a direct performance evaluation.

Subsequently, all the datasets were reprojected to the British National Grid coordinate system to ensure consistent spatial alignment across all the temperature fields. Then, the datasets were aggregated at the Greater London Area (GLA) Local Super Output Area (LSOA) level using zonal statistics to ensure compatibility with the socioeconomic and demographic data required for the spatial vulnerability analysis.

Figure 1 Daily mean, maximum, and minimum temperatures averaged over the period 10 to 25 July 2022

Crowd-Grid integrates observations from the Met Office network with crowdsourced and third-party stations, resulting in denser spatial coverage across urban areas compared to the standard HadUK-Grid dataset, though with higher associated uncertainty (UK, 2025).

Finally, since the Crowd-Grid dataset and WRF produced the closest results, the last part of the study, which focuses on the spatial vulnerability analysis of GLA, aims to highlight differences in temperature distribution and exposure patterns derived from these high-resolution datasets and their implications for identifying vulnerable populations and infrastructure. For this purpose, various socio-economic and demographic indicators, including population age, income levels, multiple indices of deprivation, housing, and tenure types, were combined with temperature data to identify areas where the intersection of extreme thermal stress and social vulnerability is most pronounced.

3. Results

The comparative analysis reveals that while all three datasets captured the evolution of the heatwave, the Crowd-Grid dataset and the WRF output showed a higher degree of spatial heterogeneity in temperature fields than the relatively smoother gradients inherent in the standard HadUK-Grid interpolation, as shown in Figure 1.

Nevertheless, given the statistical relationships between the way urban land use shapes temperature distributions in the Crowd-Grid dataset and the spatial extent of the Met Office's WOW database, it is possible to identify two distinct areas affected by very high temperatures: the south-west and the north-east of London.

On the contrary, the WRF model, which incorporates a 3-D building energy parameterization scheme, shows a more homogeneous thermal pattern across the whole city, with hotspots primarily concentrated in the dense city center.

These findings are even clearer when looking at nighttime temperatures: the capability of WRF to explicitly represent urban physical processes through physically based parameterization schemes shows different patterns of the urban heat island (UHI) effect compared with the Crowd-Grid and HadUK-Grid datasets (Figure 1 - tasmin).

These discrepancies are relevant in the context of spatial vulnerability analyses, as the choice of input data significantly influences the identification of areas and populations at risk. Therefore, the same neighbourhood may be classified as highly vulnerable or moderately exposed depending solely on the adopted temperature dataset.

To address this, a bivariate choropleth map of temperature and multiple indices of deprivation is plotted for each dataset and for both maximum and minimum temperatures (Figures 2 and 3).

Figure 2 Bivariate choropleth map of tasmax and indices of multiple deprivation (IMD)

The results indicate that, during the day, while observational datasets highlight wider portions of the city as more vulnerable to heat, the modelled temperatures combined with IMD tend to identify fewer areas of extreme thermal exposure, suggesting that the interpolation methods or sensor distribution in observational networks may overestimate the spatial extent of peak heat stress compared to the physically-based simulations.

Figure 3 Choropleth bivariate map of tasmin and indices of multiple deprivation (IMD)

Hence, for the same reason, when looking at nighttime temperatures, the modelled temperatures combined with IMD tend to identify broader areas than the observational dataset, which tend to emphasize areas included in the dense and core of the city.

4. Conclusions

The divergences identified in the previous section suggest that relying solely on observational data may underestimate nighttime exposure in suburban and peri-urban zones, whereas modelled outputs provide a more comprehensive depiction of the spatial extent of the UHI effect across the entire urban agglomeration.

This highlights the importance of integrating physically based simulations with observational networks to capture the full diurnal cycle of thermal stress and ensure that vulnerability assessments account for differential exposure patterns between dense urban cores and surrounding localities.

These findings underscore the need for careful dataset selection in GIS-based heat vulnerability studies and support the integration of physically based urban climate models with emerging high-resolution observational products to inform equitable climate adaptation strategies.

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Biographies

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Dr Charles Simpson is a Senior Research Fellow at University College London, specialising in the health impacts of climate change. His work spans modelling and monitoring extreme heat in cities, assessing health risks, and evaluating strategies to mitigate heat through physical and statistical approaches.

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